

Education, inclusion, and protection: Artificial intelligence as a tool for enhancing Moroccan women's participation in the New Development Model.

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Abstract

Purpose. Over the past few decades, Morocco has made the bold choice to adopt a series of forward-looking prerogatives. Major projects in the economic, political, and social spheres are underway. The New Development Model (NMD) outlines Morocco's ambitions for 2035. None of these ambitions can be achieved without the full participation of women. However, Moroccan women and girls still face multiple obstacles: poverty, marginalization, illiteracy, and violence. This research aims to explore how AI could act as a lever to overcome the barriers that hinder the active and full participation of women in the New Development Model.

Methods. The use of an integrated theoretical framework that combines gender and development, empowerment theories and information and communication technologies for development has allowed us to draw a relevant analytical framework. For our empirical investigation, we opted for a qualitative approach throughout a focus group. A thematic analysis was carried out to identify recurring themes and to clearly delineate the main axes and the barriers encountered by women in participating in the NMD.

Results. Our analysis enabled us to identify three major strategic areas to ensure women's full participation in the NMD: literacy and education, economic empowerment, and ensuring safety and integrity. AI technologies can act as a strong lever to overcome the barriers that women may encounter in these fields. Technologies such as smart tutoring and voice recognition facilitate literacy and enables women to access future-oriented jobs by removing barriers to education. Women's economic empowerment is now more accessible through intelligent freelance platforms and automation tools that offer valuable flexibility for work-life balance while boosting social development. AI technology can also be used to prevent and combat all forms of violence. AI-powered predictive alert systems and smart video surveillance solutions can help to create a safe environment that is essential for women's economic engagement.

Implications. AI technology alone is not a complete solution for removing the barriers faced by women. It acts primarily as a catalyst for amplification, but its effectiveness remains dependent on profound structural changes. A key issue is ensuring that stakeholders can leverage this technology to enhance women's agency and capabilities, enabling them to become true agents of development.

Keywords : AI, New Development Model, Women and development, Empowerment, ICT4D.